

Global perspectives and responses to Romania's 2024-2025 presidential elections

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Abstract

The article analyses international reactions to Romania's presidential elections, focusing on the annulled vote of November 2024 and the rescheduled election in May 2025. It underscores how these developments were interpreted by Western democracies and by the revisionist authoritarian regime of the Russian Federation. One of the most contentious moments in Romania's democratic evolution since 1989, the elections prompted reactions from the United States, France, Germany, the United Kingdom, and Italy, reflecting the wider geopolitical tensions in Europe, the dynamics of international relations, and the ideological competition among major global powers during a period of profound transformation. Our hypothesis is that the external impact and attitudes of global actors toward the recent presidential elections in Romania functioned as a "mirror", reflecting hybrid warfare, significant turbulence in international politics, Russia's revisionist ambitions, and the ongoing redefinition of relations among major powers. For an area located on the geopolitical periphery of NATO and the European Union, the collapse of democratic institutions, liberal values, and the pro-Western trajectory would have sent a profound and disquieting message to the surrounding region and to Europe at large.

Keywords

Presidential elections; hybrid warfare; populism; misinformation; extremism

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Introduction

For an extended period, from its accession to the European Union in 2007 and during the Covid-19 pandemic, Romania was widely regarded as one of Europe's "disciplined students." Throughout this period, it maintained strong public support for the EU and NATO, pursued a foreign policy aligned with its Euro-Atlantic partners, and saw no representation of Eurosceptic or extremist parties in its national parliament. Episodes related to the cohabitation crises between (center-)right presidents and (center-)left parliamentary majorities, such as the failed impeachments of 2007 and 2012 or the conflicts related to the justice laws of 2017-2019, were, however, key moments amid the erosion and subsequent partial stabilization of the Romanian democratic system (Mișcoiu and Bogdan, 2021).

Although European and international attention to Romania's political developments is generally limited, the 2024 and 2025 presidential elections emerged as a political episode of notable visibility within the European context. The first round of voting, held in November 2024, was affected by allegations of interference and disinformation in favor of the previously almost unknown far-right candidate, Călin Georgescu, and, consequently, by the unprecedented decision of the Constitutional Court to invalidate the elections. The episode culminated in the rescheduling of the presidential elections for May 2025, ultimately resulting in a narrow victory for the centrist, pro-European candidate, Nicușor Dan, who had as opponent another national-populist candidate, George Simion, in the second round.

The events generated widespread media coverage and official responses across numerous countries, structured around two main axes: (a) concern for the integrity of the democratic process (especially for the vulnerabilities created by disinformation and hybrid attacks) and (b) geopolitical considerations regarding Romania's external orientation in relation to the EU and NATO. The decision of the Constitutional Court of Romania (CCR) to cancel the November 2024 elections was the focal point of external analysis and triggered security reports and interpretations at the level of specialized think tanks. The positions of the world's states towards the elections in Romania were, however, different: while Russia vehemently criticized the cancellation of the November elections and openly supported the far-right candidates, and the USA changed its position significantly between the Biden and Trump Administrations, the EU member states consistently aligned themselves with the liberal and democratic camp, endorsing the "cordon sanitaire" strategy employed by pro-European parties and candidates to counter extremist forces.

In this paper, following a concise overview of the political context relevant to the period under study, we will proceed to analyze the manner in which the political leadership, the main media institutions and public opinions from several geopolitically relevant states reacted to the political developments in electoral Romania (November 2024 - May 2025): the USA, Russia, Great Britain, Germany, France, and Italy.

The political context of the presidential elections of December 2024 and May 2025

From September 2021 to May 2025, Romania was under the leadership of a unique "grand coalition" formed by the Social Democratic Party (PSD) and the National Liberal Party (PNL). The advantage of such a governmental formula was, without a doubt, political stability, but the price paid for it was the creation of a large space favorable to the growth of a radical and nationalist opposition, represented by the Alliance for the Unification of Romanians (AUR) and SOS Romania, to the detriment of the other liberal and pro-European opposition, embodied by the Union for the Salvation of Romania (USR). In contrast to their joint approach during the June 2024 European Parliament elections, where the two major parties ran successfully on a common list, the PNL and PSD failed to reach an agreement for the

presidential and parliamentary elections held later that year. Instead, they presented separate candidates and lists, yet coordinated the electoral timeline in a way that served their mutual interests: the single round of the parliamentary elections was scheduled between the two rounds of the presidential elections, so the chances of the two parties securing a parliamentary majority, as well as their representatives, Prime Minister Marcel Ciolacu (PSD) and PNL leader Nicolae Ciucă, advancing to the second round, increased significantly (Orosz, 2024).

In November 2024, however, amid the erosion of the government coalition, the prospect of an austerity budget in 2025, and the fragmentation of the political spectrum caused by the proliferation of presidential candidates, Romania experienced an unexpected electoral outcome: a little-known far-right anti-system candidate, Călin Georgescu, surprisingly won the first round of the presidential elections, with approximately 23% of the votes, followed by the USR candidate, Elena Lasconi, while the PSD, PNL, and AUR candidates were eliminated from the electoral race. Whereas Lasconi's second-place finish can be partly attributed to strategic voting by numerous PNL supporters, the unexpectedly strong performance of Călin Georgescu remains a point of contention among political analysts. A shared explanation for this unexpected development points to a large-scale TikTok campaign, coordinated by influencer networks and subsequently interpreted by Romanian security services as instruments of Russian influence (ComunitateaLiberala.ro, 2025). Consequently, on December 6, 2024, the Constitutional Court of Romania (CCR) annulled the results of the first round, citing reasons related to external interference and violation of electoral laws. The decision caused a deep political crisis, marking a precedent in recent Romanian democratic history.

At the same time, the parliamentary elections held on December 1 failed to produce a clear majority for any single political party, yet they marked the entry of three right-wing extremist parties into the Parliament: AUR (19%), SOS Romania (7%) and the Party of Young People (POT, 6%, close to Călin Georgescu). The pro-European parties, which lost massive votes in the 2020 parliamentary elections, formed a majority coalition without the extremist parties, but also without the USR, dissatisfied with the cancellation of the elections and the government's lack of reformist ambition. The new government, aimed at maintaining stability, was led by the PSD leader, Marcel Ciolacu.

Under these circumstances, Romania witnessed a wave of protests between December 2024 and May 2025, some of which were notably significant, especially in Bucharest. AUR, together with other pro-Georgescu actors, mobilized thousands of people to denounce the "anti-democratic actions" and to demand the resignation of the PSD, PNL, and UDMR majority government (Nemeş and Costiţă, 2025). In parallel, tensions at the institutional level increased. President Klaus Iohannis, whose term was extended until new elections were held, was forced to resign in February 2025, to avoid a possible impeachment, and the interim presidency was taken over by the new PNL leader, Ilie Bolojan, as President of the Senate.

The presidential elections, set to resume in May 2025, were preceded by the disqualification of Călin Georgescu, who was accused of anti-constitutional actions. Four candidates were credited with greater chances by polling institutes: George Simion (AUR deputy), Nicușor Dan (independent, mayor of Bucharest, pro-European centrist), Crin Antonescu (supported by the ruling coalition Romania Forward Alliance PNL-PSD-UDMR) and Victor Ponta (independent, ex-PSD deputy, sovereigntist). AUR optimized popular frustration against the political elite, practicing populist rhetoric and an anti-establishment discourse, which allowed Simion to obtain almost 42% in the first round, followed, surprisingly, by Nicușor Dan, with half of Simion's votes, narrowly ahead of Antonescu and distancing Ponta (13%). The confrontation for the second round included a significant geopolitical dimension: while Simion called himself a "sovereigntist", though defending a neutral attitude towards

the EU, NATO, Russia, and Ukraine, and trying to attract the sympathies of ultra-conservative circles in Europe and America, Nicușor Dan adopted a pro-EU and pro-NATO discourse, criticizing Russia's aggression against Ukraine and trying to mobilize civil society and young people. Following a large popular mobilization, Dan won with 54%, although he lost in the diaspora by the same score. After a long period of preliminary talks and negotiations, the PSD-PNL-UDMR government coalition was reformed, being completed by USR, founded by the newly elected president. The new government, led by Ilie Bolojan and installed in June 2025, is now forced to propose and implement a large reform and austerity program, given the extremely difficult macro-economic situation.

International perspectives on the Romanian presidential elections

Internationally, Romania tends to receive limited attention and visibility. Its internal political life is not usually widely covered in the international media. Especially after joining NATO (2004) and the EU (2007), the dominant external perception was that of a country on the geopolitical margins of the Western sphere, but otherwise marked by stability, consistency, and an absence of dramatic shifts. For several decades, Romania seemed to be firmly anchored (Stan, 2025), although not without vulnerabilities, in the fundamental pro-Western strategic option adopted after the fall of communism.

However, interest in the Romanian presidential elections rose unexpectedly after November 24, 2024, drawing intense attention from political circles and media outlets across Europe, the United States, and Russia. Coverage and commentary reached levels virtually unseen during the past 35 years, driven primarily by the unprecedented emergence - since the fall of communism - of a viable anti-Western, pro-Russian candidate whose potential victory threatened to alter Romania's traditionally pro-Western political trajectory. The only previous instance of an extremist nationalist candidate reaching the second round of Romania's presidential election occurred in December 2000, when Corneliu Vadim Tudor qualified but was never considered a serious contender, ultimately obtaining only one-third of the vote against Ion Iliescu. In contrast, the 2024–2025 elections marked a dramatic shift: polls indicated that Călin Georgescu held a clear lead over Elena Lasconi (Dinu, 2024), transforming the situation into a potential crisis, not only for Romania's democratic stability and political orientation, but also for the cohesion of the European Union and NATO.

International interest intensified all the more given that Romania's unusual electoral episode in 2024, and the ensuing political crisis, unfolded against the backdrop of the ongoing war in Ukraine, Russia's intense hybrid war against Western democracies, the EU and NATO, and the rise of several nationalist, sovereigntist, illiberal, or truly extremist movements in the Euro-Atlantic space. Increases in the radical anti-system current had also been reported in the same period, at values of over 20%, in various types of elections (European, general legislative, regional) in France, Germany, the Netherlands, Austria, Belgium, etc. In October 2024, amid the campaign for the pro-EU referendum in the Republic of Moldova, authorities in Chișinău uncovered and stopped a large-scale operation aimed at bribing voters with Russian funds to vote against the initiative.

From a European and regional standpoint, the rise of the sovereigntist populist wave in Romania should not have come as a surprise, yet it did. It was startling that Călin Georgescu, virtually unknown to most Romanians just two months earlier, qualified for the second round of the presidential election. His surge, largely unnoticed by opinion polls, culminated in an explosive rise (ExpertForum, 2024) to approximately 23% in the final days of the campaign and on election day itself, driven by an ultra-intense promotion on TikTok. The result was a shock even in Romania. Although the result deeply unsettled Romania's political elite, media, and society, the surprise was even more pronounced on the international stage.

Călin Georgescu and, to a large extent, later, George Simion, were prominent figures within this populist, extremist current, propagating violence, primarily through rhetoric, but also by issuing threats involving the use of force and calls for revenge against the "corrupt globalist elites". They belonged to a movement rooted in fascist (legionary) ideology and infused with elements of communist nostalgia, conspiracism and denialism, abundantly fueled by Russia through social networks in recent years (Mișcoiu and Erdei, 2025).

Media coverage and the views of key political actors in the regions mentioned were naturally shaped by their interests, ideological leanings, and the current, whether pro-status quo or revisionist, they aligned with. In practice, each leader or party in the countries analyzed seemed to politically associate themselves with the discourse or cause of one of the major candidates, aligning with their values, principles, orientation, or the type of electorate they represented, even if such alignment was not always explicitly expressed. However, in Russia's case, the assumption regarding Călin Georgescu was unmistakable, especially after November 24, as the following analysis will demonstrate.

In the second round of the resumed elections, on May 18, 2025, Nicușor Dan received clear support from the leaders of France, Germany, the EU, Great Britain, the Republic of Moldova, the Polish government, etc. Reduced to the scale of national politics, the dramatic electoral episode in Romania reproduced quite faithfully the Ukraine versus Russia rifts in international politics, but also the "globalists versus sovereigntists" or centrists versus populist-extremists disputes in the democracies of the Western space. This analysis will continue with an examination of how Romania's presidential elections were covered in political discourse and media narratives across the United States, Europe, and the Russian Federation.

The United States of America. A clear distinction must be drawn from the outset between the reporting issued by the Biden administration, in the final phase of its mandate, concerning the Romanian elections held on November 24, 2024, and the reporting provided by the incoming Trump administration after January 20, 2025. For Romania, a country with a longstanding alliance with the United States, the sudden shift in tone and the largely negative reactions from key Trump administration officials, as well as from influencers affiliated with MAGA circles, regarding the Constitutional Court's decisions to annul the presidential elections and subsequently prohibit a renewed candidacy by the pro-Russian extremist Călin Georgescu, came as a shock.

On December 4, 2024, just four days before the second round, the Supreme Council for National Defense (CSAT) made the surprising and spectacular decision to declassify a recent Report, which explicitly spoke of "the actions of a state cyber actor and Russian cybercrime platforms" (Presidential Administration, 2024) that altered the electoral process, including through "swarming" (swarms of messages) and a "mass guerilla political campaign" on TikTok, in favor of candidate Călin Georgescu.

On December 4 and 5, 2024, just before the CCR's decision to cancel the December 6 elections, the US State Department, through spokesman Matthew Miller, and then Secretary of State Blinken, expressed clear concerns about Russia's influence on the Romanian presidential elections. On December 4, the US Embassy in Bucharest disseminated the press release from Washington, expressing concern that a possible change in Romania's orientation would have serious negative consequences on US-Romania security cooperation:

„We are concerned by the Romanian Supreme Council for National Defense (CSAT)'s report of Russian involvement in malign cyber activity designed to influence the integrity of the Romanian electoral process. Data referenced in the report should be fully investigated to ensure the integrity of Romania's electoral process. The United States values Romania's

contributions as a strong NATO ally and partner in the European Union. Romania's hard-earned progress anchoring itself in the Transatlantic community cannot be turned back by foreign actors seeking to shift Romania's foreign policy away from its Western alliances. Any such change would have serious negative impacts on U.S. security cooperation with Romania, while a decision to restrict foreign investment would discourage U.S. companies from continuing to invest in Romania" (US Embassy in Romania, 2024).

In turn, US Secretary of State Antony Blinken, who was at an OSCE meeting on December 5, stated that "Romanian authorities have uncovered a substantial and well-financed Russian campaign aimed at influencing the recent presidential elections, in violation of OSCE standards" (Vulcan, 2024). On the other hand, during that time, unverified reports emerged suggesting that Western intelligence agencies, most notably American ones, provided Romania's CSAT with valuable and strategic information about Russia's interference and attack on the November 24 elections.

A few hours after the CCR's decision on December 6 to cancel the first round of the presidential elections, the State Department returned with a new statement, suggesting the Biden administration's agreement with the decision taken and explicitly mentioning its confidence in Romania's democracy: "The United States reaffirms our confidence in Romania's democratic institutions and processes, including investigations into foreign malign influence" (Sarbu and Taco, 2024).

However, the United States' previously benevolent and supportive stance shifted following the inauguration of the Trump administration, on January 20, 2025. On February 14, at the Munich Security Conference, Vice President J.D. Vance made harsh and surprising statements about what happened, saying that:

"Romania annulled its presidential elections based on tenuous claims from an intelligence agency and amid intense pressure from neighboring European states. [...] I was struck by the fact that a former European commissioner recently appeared on television and seemed delighted that the Romanian government had just cancelled an entire election. He warned that if things did not go according to plan, the same scenario could repeat in Germany." (Costiță et al., 2025)

This criticism, issued by the second-highest official in the White House, marked a downturn in Romania's diplomatic rapport with the United States. Shortly thereafter, the fears were confirmed, with Romania being suspended from the Visa Waiver program, into which it had been introduced at the end of the Biden administration, albeit after the new American authorities announced that they had carried out a "technical assessment." Additionally, Elon Musk, briefly and controversially the head of DOGE, voiced strong criticism of the CCR's decision to annul the elections, directing his indignation at then-president Marian Enache: "This guy is a tyrant, not a judge", a statement made at the same conference of American conservatives to which Vice President JD Vance returned with a criticism of the Romanian authorities:

"The point that I try to make to our European friends is ... that friendship is based on shared values. You don't have shared values if you cancel elections because you don't like the result, and that happened in Romania. If you're so afraid of your own people that you silence them and shut them up." (Reuters, 2025)

It should be pointed out here, however, that Elon Musk has also made harsh criticisms (and received appropriate responses) of the governments of Great Britain and Germany, the President of France (Henley, 2025) or the Foreign Minister of Poland. He also explicitly supported the right-wing extremist AfD party in the German elections in February 2025.

Presidents Joe Biden and Donald Trump did not make direct references to the cancelled presidential elections in Romania. After the inauguration of President Nicușor Dan, following the elections in May 2025, President Trump called President Dan and congratulated him, inviting him to pay an official visit to the USA (Grădinaru and Cornea, 2025). It was already a point at which the crisis of trust between the United States and Romania began to show signs of resolution.

Germany. Germany, like the United States, underwent both general elections and a change in leadership within a few months. The elections were held in February 2025, and on May 6, coinciding with the interval between Romania's two resumed presidential rounds, a new government took office under Chancellor Friedrich Merz. Neither the old Scholz government nor the new Merz government had any positions on the cancellation of the presidential elections in Romania, and Berlin's silence was interpreted by public opinion rather as a tacit approval.

It should be noted that the CDU leader came after several exchanges of blunt remarks with several new officials of the Washington administration, especially with Elon Musk (Deutsche Welle, 2024b), who had expressed support in the German electoral campaign for the extremist AfD party while also reacting against the cancellation of the elections in Romania.

On December 6, Deutsche Welle's international edition confined its coverage to a neutral account of the news concerning the annulment of Romania's presidential elections, noting, however, that Georgescu is a far-right populist who praised the Romanian fascist (legionary) movement during World War II:

„Romania's constitutional court on Friday annulled the results of the first round of the country's presidential election, when far-right populist Calin Georgescu emerged as the surprise front-runner. Georgescu, an independent candidate who declared zero campaign spending, was polling in single digits soon before the election, but surged to just under 23% of the vote. [...] Romanian authorities declassified intelligence on Wednesday alleging "aggressive hybrid Russian attacks," saying there were coordinated campaigns on influential accounts on TikTok and Telegram to promote Georgescu. Georgescu, the surprise first-round winner, was a leading member of AUR until the party expelled him for being too radical, after his praise for a Romanian fascist movement during World War II." (Deutsche Welle, 2024a)

However, in January 2025, the daily *Frankfurter Allgemeine Zeitung* took a rather skeptical approach to the annulment of the elections, rhetorically asking how valid “the myth of Russian interference and how arrogant the Romanian authorities were” (von Michael, 2025) was. The article emerged amid an intense early effort to uncover “evidence” of Russian involvement - an endeavor complicated by the limitations of basic technical analyses of TikTok posts. The „discernible footprint” of Călin Georgescu's supporters, reflected in millions of views, messages, likes, and even financial backing, appeared to originate from individual users or companies based in Vietnam, Indonesia, South Africa, the United Kingdom, and other countries. The presence of message multipliers and operational hubs on TikTok appeared to be in countries geographically distant from the region, an arrangement that is easily achievable in virtual space and does not exclude the possibility of a central command structure for the entire operation being based in Russia.

Immediately after the second round on May 18, Chancellor Merz congratulated the elected President Nicușor Dan, emphasizing the pro-European dimension of this victory: “Romania has committed to a strong and safe Europe: Dear @NicusorDanRO, congratulations on your electoral victory!” (Panaitescu, 2025) Germany's message of rapprochement with Romania, following the presidential elections in May 2025, was reiterated during President Nicușor Dan's official visit to Berlin

on July 18. Russian interference in the elections was reiterated. Chancellor Merz's statements were as clear as could be:

"For several years, we have been witnessing an even greater increase in attempts by Russia and other countries to divide the EU, to weaken the transatlantic alliance and to misinform society and public opinion. I believe that this is one of the greatest challenges that we, liberal democracies, are facing. [...] The tangible nature of such an attack was evident in Romania during the first round of the presidential elections. I followed the electoral process in Romania with close and deliberate attention, which, this time too, in the second round, were massively influenced by entities from Russia, but democracy in Romania was, fortunately, strong enough and managed to respond with an electoral campaign that resulted in the president who is visiting us today." (Lazăr, 2025).

Russia. During the election campaign, Moscow sought to project an image of neutrality regarding the outcome of the Romanian presidential elections, refraining from overt support for any candidate. However, immediately following the elections, Russian media coverage revealed clear and explicit backing (G4 Media, 2024) for Călin Georgescu, despite longstanding indications of his growing proximity to Russia. Georgescu has been a politically volatile figure, pursuing various strategies over time to secure a prominent role. At one stage, he was nominated by the Alliance for the Union of Romanians (AUR) for the position of prime minister, a rift between him and the party occurred (Pavel, 2022).

Georgescu had travelled to Moscow several times, starting in January 2016 (G4 Media, 2025a), showing sympathy for Russia and Vladimir Putin. He also expressed especially virulent criticism of NATO and the EU, being praised by the pro-Kremlin press, including Sputnik and Russia Today, especially with a speech in which he stated that "there is no freedom in Romania" (Stancu, 2025). This declared "independent" candidate had in fact been, as subsequent reports proved, "Russia's candidate" (Fati, 2024) in the 2024 presidential elections.

The day after the annulment of the elections, Russian Foreign Minister Sergei Lavrov commented critically on the situation in Romania, saying that "the Constitutional Court of Romania acted in accordance with an order, in a manner reminiscent of military obedience, ultimately resulting in the annulment of the elections. A similar situation occurred in Ukraine, in 2004" (Cojan, 2024). Lavrov said of Călin Georgescu, in the same statement, that he had never praised Russia but was only a candidate who "does not curse Russia," suggesting that this would be unacceptable in a Romania controlled by Western powers. The same type of criticism regarding the annulment of the elections and especially the subsequent elimination by the CCR of Călin Georgescu, in March 2025, was formulated by Dmitri Peskov, the Kremlin spokesman:

"In Romania, a candidate may win the presidential elections, yet it is essential that he be perceived as unsuitable—particularly if he is open to dialogue with Russia. Consequently, he is dismissed. Who criticized Romania for this? The answer is straightforward: we no longer accept lessons from Europeans. We reject guidance from those who act with hypocrisy!" (G4 Media, 2025b)

Prior to the Kremlin's statement, it is noteworthy that Russia's foreign intelligence service took an unusually political position by openly endorsing Călin Georgescu. In its declaration, titled "Romania: EU crackdown on dissent reaches new level," the agency warned of "EU blackmail if Georgescu were allowed to be a candidate":

“Ursula von der Leyen, who played a major role in invalidating the results of the first round of the elections for the head of state in Romania at the end of 2024, has called on the current authorities in Bucharest not to allow Georgescu to participate in the subsequent round of vote in May of this year. She threatened to restrict Romania's access to EU funds if the representative of “non-systemic forces” continues to participate in the electoral campaign”. (Cârlugea, 2025)

A clearer statement of Russia's support for Călin Georgescu cannot exist, especially since it was made by an institution that usually does not declare anything publicly without the Kremlin's consent.

France. Assuming the position of the main defender of liberal and democratic principles and promoter of Europeanization, France supported the positions of the pro-European majority in Bucharest, placing the surprising evolution of the neophyte anti-system candidate Călin Georgescu in the wake of the hybrid war practiced by Russia against the democratic states that support Ukraine. Thus, the official responses from France reflected two prevailing tones.

On the one hand, French officials expressed support for the observance of Romania's democratic procedures, underscoring the Constitutional Court's role as a stabilizing institution and a safeguard of democratic legitimacy. In response to the annulment of the November 2024 presidential election, President Macron emphasized that:

“[...] the election was dishonest, the first round was cancelled, which is unprecedented [...] We thought that our democratic system was very solid, but because today we get our information from social networks, we can be manipulated by propaganda, on a very large scale. And, in a way, those who developed this power are better armed than us. That is why we must provide answers [...] I was not shocked by the Court's decision, what shocks me is that Russia massively influenced the honesty of the elections in Romania” (Le Petit Journal, 2025).

On the other hand, we witnessed the public condemnation of unfounded theses regarding the interference of some Western actors in limiting the right of some extremist candidates to run for office, with reference to Diana Șoșoacă and, subsequently, to Călin Georgescu (Syfuss-Arnaud, 2025). Targeted by Russia, France has faced accusations from Telegram founder Pavel Durov, who claimed that French authorities urged the platform to suppress conservative viewpoints. These accusations have been denied by the French Foreign Intelligence Service (DGSE) and the French Foreign Ministry and denounced as part of a broader Russian plan to discredit the electoral process in European countries and destabilize the EU as a whole. The French Ambassador to Romania, Nicolas Warnery, explicitly highlighted Russia's attempts to discredit his country and the difference between the roles played by the two states in Romania's historical evolution:

"Look at the cemeteries where those who fell on the battlefield are buried. Who invaded Romania? Who forbade Romania a democratic experience after World War II? Who invaded Ukraine? This is Russia. Who helped Romania in the 19th century to create a national state? Who helped Romania in World War I? Who became a framework nation of the Atlantic Alliance in 2022? Who proposed to Romania the creation of a defense industry through cooperation? Who protects Romania at Cape Midia? Who supported Romania in entering the Schengen Area? Who supports Romania in joining the OECD? That is France. Russia accuses others of what it itself does. It is an old Russian technique. If someone colonized Romania in history, that was Russia, not France” (Nahoi, 2025).

French media framed the Romanian case as a lesson for European democracies, highlighting not only the coverage of events like cancellations and reruns, but also prompting deeper consideration

of digital vulnerabilities and how well institutions can withstand hybrid threats. The most important French publications dedicated consistent analyses to the phenomenon, interpreting the cancellation of the election as a signal that constitutional mechanisms, even if rarely used, can restore some of the public trust, if applied transparently. In addition, French journalists revealed the scale of disinformation and manipulation circulating across digital platforms, in many cases transnationalized through social media (Radio France, 2025).

In the French media and society, there was intense discussion about the fact that a victory of the far right in Romania would imply changes in foreign policy, in the sense of increasing euroscepticism and diminishing support for Ukraine, as well as producing a possible contagion effect on other European democracies (Danes, 2024). French observers have reacted carefully to the regional consequences, recommending, in foreign policy commentaries, a series of measures to strengthen sectoral resilience (electoral infrastructure, transparent regulation of political financing, EU-NATO cooperation in information security).

Italy. In Italy, the reporting was framed primarily through the lens of domestic political dynamics. The government in Rome, led in 2025 by a coalition comprising the far right, radical right, and conservative right, exhibited a plurality of responses, ranging from expressions of concern, predominantly conveyed through mainstream media outlets, to more restrained or nuanced tones observed in media affiliated with far-right currents. Publications such as *Corriere della Sera* reflected concerns about Euro-Atlantic stability, while Italian commentators made comparisons between populist tactics in Romania and those present in Italy (Muglia, 2025).

Italy's response to the annulment of the Romanian elections was delayed and characterized by a notable disjunction between the actions of political actors and their public statements. Thus, in March 2025, almost three months after the cancellation of the elections, the Italian Ambassador to Bucharest, Alfredo Maria Durante, declared that:

"We have been attentively monitoring developments in recent weeks, particularly after the annulment of the first round of the presidential elections. It has become increasingly evident that the manipulation of information originating from external sources, alongside deliberate foreign interference, has significantly impacted Romania's democratic electoral process. The risk is very high due to the fact that foreign entities exploit the cracks in the internal society. While such phenomena are not confined to Romania, the Romanian case has offered particularly revealing insights. Through a careful analysis of the trajectory and sentiment of public opinion, it has become evident how vulnerabilities can be exploited." (Groza, 2025)

During that same week, Prime Minister Giorgia Meloni hosted a summit of sovereigntist parties (Atreju), where she also met the leader of the Romanian far-right, George Simion, whose party, AUR, is a partner of the Fratelli d'Italia formation within the European Conservatives and Reformists group in the Strasbourg Parliament (Coșlea, 2025).

After the elections won in May 2025 by the Euro-Atlantic-oriented candidate, the political ambiguity gave way to a clear official reaction, marked, however, by a clearly diplomatic-protocol tone: Prime Minister Giorgia Meloni congratulated Nicușor Dan immediately after the announcement of the results, emphasizing the availability of constructive cooperation between Rome and Bucharest. This official reaction, expressed through public messages by the Italian leaders (president and prime minister), highlighted the desire for a stable and pragmatic-strategic relationship between the two states, reducing the risk of a hostile reading of the vote result (Andreșescu, 2025). Rome's official reaction, one of congratulations and a call for cooperation, was intended to maintain stability in the

bilateral relationship and avoid escalating regional political tensions. However, the reaction contrasts with the statements made by the leader of the main coalition partner, Deputy Prime Minister Matteo Salvini (La Liga), who accused an "unprecedented electoral fraud":

„Honor to our friend George Simion, who in the presidential elections in Romania — where he, as voted for by the majority of Romanians in Italy, fought to the end, against everything and everyone, following an unprecedented theft of democracy. Keep going, @georgesimion!” (Salvini, 2025)

Italian analysts explored the rhetorical convergences between populist movements in Eastern Europe and those in Italy (anti-elite rhetoric, appeals to the diaspora, identity narratives), but they also highlighted the limits of transferability: the Romanian socio-economic context, marked by fiscal problems, a crisis of confidence, creates a distinct dynamic (CISE, 2025).

The United Kingdom. The reaction of Great Britain, as expressed by Ambassador Giles Matthew Portman, differed from those of France and Germany and was one of a cautious balance between concern about the political situation generated by the cancellation of the elections and the need to clarify the reasons that underpinned such an unprecedented decision:

“An election isn’t cancelled without a very strong reason. When the Romanian government informed us of serious concerns regarding the election’s integrity and potential Russian interference, we were clearly concerned and took the matter very seriously [...] What is important is that only Romanians have the right to choose their president, and that the election must be free and fair. There were clearly concerns that, although the vote was free, it was not necessarily fair” (Cochino, 2025).

The formal reactions of the British executive were relatively cautious and focused more on bilateral dialogue, culminating in official congratulations to the president-elect and continuing with further diplomatic contacts, including meetings in NATO format. Direct messages from the embassy and some government representatives marked the continued support for cooperation in the areas of security and justice, without publicly interpreting the events in an offensive or accusatory key. We can therefore observe that the approach oriented towards diplomatic stability and maintaining the continuity of bilateral relations dominated.

The British media covered the events in Romania from the perspective of Euro-Atlantic security and stability: the predominant themes were the possible erosion of Romania's support for Ukraine in the event of a victory of the far right, the risk of disinformation dissemination and the consequences for NATO/EU cohesion. British organizations and think tanks (including CSIS commentators and other Euro-Atlantic platforms) amplified discussions on the need for a coordinated response to hybrid attacks (Bergmann and Ruy, 2025).

The British media and some political analysts have mentioned the contribution and influence of the Romanian diaspora in the electoral dynamics: transnational mobilization, the circulation of narratives on social networks and the capacity of diasporic flows to amplify disinformation (Cuckson, 2024). Given the presence of a significant Romanian community in the UK, diplomatic reactions have been sensitive to protecting the right to participate, but also to the risks of spreading false narratives across borders (Jones and Nilsson-Julien, 2025).

Conclusions

External perceptions and international coverage of the Romanian presidential elections of 2024 and 2025 reflect quite accurately the ideological and strategic faults existing in world politics. The greatest

impact and the most substantial reactions were recorded, as was predictable, in Europe, the USA and Russia. Some states adopted more reserved stances during the 2024 elections and the subsequent post-cancellation crisis, such as Germany, Great Britain, and Italy, while others took clear positions. Several supported Romania in the challenging decisions made by the Constitutional Court (including the USA until January 20, 2025, France, and the EU as a whole), whereas others criticized those decisions (notably Russia and the USA after January 20, 2025).

In the second round of elections, on May 18, 2025, some countries refrained from expressing support for any candidate at the leadership level (such as the USA and Russia), while most European states voiced their support for Nicușor Dan. Hungary presented a distinct case, wherein Prime Minister Viktor Orbán initially expressed support for George Simion. This position was promptly and emphatically challenged by Kelemen Hunor, the leader of the Democratic Alliance of Hungarians in Romania (UDMR), a party representing the Hungarian minority in Romania, who openly supported Nicușor Dan. Subsequently, Viktor Orbán withdrew his statement.

Between November 2024 and May 2025, Romania experienced a deeply dramatic and destabilizing democratic crisis that placed heavy strain on its institutions, political parties and leaders, independent candidates, the media, and society at large. It represented the most challenging and crisis-ridden episode in Romania's post-communist history. Despite the continued presence of extremist and anti-system movements, Nicușor Dan's unexpected and remarkable electoral victory, followed by the formation of a new pro-European coalition, gave democracy in Romania a renewed, and potentially last, chance for recovery.

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